

Characterization and simulation of AlSi10Mg reinforcement structures by DED-LB/P

Francesco Bruzzo¹, Matteo Alberghini², Andrea Bertinetti², Alessio Tommasi², Mirko Riede¹, Daniele Pullini³, Elena López¹

¹ Fraunhofer, Institut für Werkstoff und Strahltechnik, Winterbergstraße 28, 01277 Dresden, Germany

² Gemmate Technologies Srl, Buttigliera Alta 10090, Italy

³ Centro Ricerche Fiat, Str. Torino 50, Orbassano 10043, Italy

1 Abstract

Amongst metal additive manufacturing technologies, Direct Energy Deposition (DED) processes have the advantage to be easily integrable in a manufacturing chain with other conventional technologies. This characteristic can be exploited by designing reinforcement structures to be added by DED onto pre-existing subcomponents to tailor the part's mechanical properties while keeping the part lightweight. This study focuses on DED by means of laser beam and powder (DED-LB/P) process optimization to improve material quality and geometrical accuracy of AlSi₁₀Mg reinforcement structures while preventing excessive thermal deformations and material dilution into the substrate. These results are compared with finite elements numerical simulations of the deposition process, comprising thermo-elastic deformation and material deposition, to predict the bending and reinforcement of the processed substrate. In particular, the model includes the deterministic prediction of the deposition profile as a function of the process parameters and a few condition-specific coefficients: once calibrated, the model was used to compare the numerical and experimental residual deformation of the reinforced sample, obtaining promising agreement. The reinforcement provided to a 1.5 mm thick substrate by a single wall of deposited material, with cross sectional dimensions of 2 mm in width and 2.5 mm in height, was evaluated by 3 points bending. With the reinforcement on the tensile side of the stresses, the energy absorbed by the material plastic deformation increased by 2.4% as compared to the substrate alone, while with the reinforcement on the compression side of the stresses the energy absorption increased by 75.8% on average.

Key words: Direct Energy Deposition, aluminium, reinforcements, plastic deformation, energy absorption, process simulation, thermal deformations

2 Introduction

2.1 DED-LB/P of aluminium alloys

The working principles of DED processes consists in a simultaneous delivery of energy and material through a nozzle to generate a melt pool on top of the underneath substrate in which new feedstock material is added. The most used energy sources are lasers, electricity or electron beams while metallic feedstock material is usually in form of powder or wire [1]. Amongst the different DED technologies, the combined use of a laser beam and metal powder (DED-LB/P) achieves the highest level of control of the thermal input given by the process. This critical feature of the process is increasingly more important when material is added on top of thin substrates with low heat dissipation capabilities and high risk of excessive thermal distortions. The processability of Al alloys by means of laser-based AM technologies, however, presents great challenges mainly due to high thermal conductivity and reflectivity of aluminium powders. Material defects, such as spherical gas pores, lack of fusion and inclusions, and low geometrical accuracy are frequent defects due to the low melting point and density, promoting high liquidity of the melt pool with low surface tension [2, 3]. Moreover, the relatively high coefficient of thermal expansion of aluminium alloys results in higher thermally-induced deformations in those processes characterized by localized high thermal gradients, such as in DED-LB/P.

On top of the challenges given by the laser-aluminium interaction and the high liquidity of the melt pool, molten aluminium is prone to solidify with high amount of material defects when in contact with oxygen and hydrogen from the atmosphere. Oxygen reacts with aluminium in an exothermic reaction that forms an oxide layer on top of the melt pool which further reduces the surface tension and interacts differently with the laser, leading to temperature increase and formation of vapors detrimental for the process stability [4, 5]. Hydrogen, on the other hand, has high solubility in liquid aluminium which strongly decreases during the solidification process. Therefore, the hydrogen diluted in the melt pool tends to regain its gaseous form, forming bubbles in the melt pool which become pores in the solidified aluminium [6, 7]. Processing of aluminium alloys, although it has been proven feasible in normal atmospheric conditions [8], is preferable under inert atmosphere to achieve a more stable process and higher material quality.

2.2 DED of reinforcement structures

Traditional methods used in the production of aluminium parts typically involve an initial forming process, subsequently followed by a subtractive manufacturing step such as cutting or machining. These procedures tend to be associated with considerable material wastage and the sequence of these processes, often performed in different locations, is a significant contributor to the extensive consumption of energy and other resources. In contrast, additive manufacturing (AM) technologies can create intricate near-net-shape components starting from a more limited range of raw feedstock materials, which are usually in powder or wire forms, resulting in a more efficient use of materials [9]. This benefit is primarily attributed to a more streamlined supply chain and the achievement of greater efficiency in the use of materials [10], particularly when compared with traditional subtractive technologies in manufacturing highly complex geometries. While powder bed AM technologies can manufacture parts with highly complex geometries, direct energy deposition (DED) technologies have the advantage of being able to add material to pre-existing subcomponents. This characteristic of the process allows to add material layer-by-layer only where needed onto a part used as substrate material, following a design analysis of the reinforcements that can aim to minimize the weight of the part while tailoring its mechanical properties as desired. This is in contrast with conventional processes where the design is usually limited by the manufacturing capabilities and the used alloy depends on the required mechanical properties. Tailored reinforcement structure's geometries are created using advanced algorithms that determine the best distribution of material within a given design space to achieve specific performance objectives [11, 12]. Algorithms-based design must be developed through a comprehensive analysis incorporating DED by means of laser beam and powder (DED-LB/P) manufacturing constrains, performance requirements and possible influence of the DED process on the pre-existing subcomponent used as substrate material for the deposition [13]. These last points present a significant challenge addressed in the study, since the DED-LB/P material is characterized by a microstructure and subsequent material properties that high function of the manufacturing conditions. Tailored material testing to measure the actual material properties are, in most cases, necessary.

2.3 Process simulation of DED-LB/P

Modeling additive manufacturing processes can be challenging and computationally expensive when all the physical phases involved are explicitly considered. In the context of DED-LB/P, the simulation of the interaction between the powder particles deposited or falling onto the substrate, their interaction with the incident laser beam, and the fluid dynamic phenomena relevant in the melt pool region require to limit the simulation domain to a few millimeters and the process time to few seconds. These scales may be optimal to evaluate the performance of the deposition process at the microscale, for example in keyhole formation [14], multi-material mass transfer [15], metallurgical conditions after solidification [16, 17], or momentum transfer between deposited particles and the melt pool [18]; however, the pursuit of extreme accuracy leads to the inability to investigate the deposition performance at an application-oriented scale.

With the goal of enhancing the mechanical performance of existing parts, attention should shift to the deposited material-substrate interaction and how the process itself damages or deforms the substrate. Furthermore, modeling can aid product development by replacing experimental testing with numerical

simulations. However, finding the optimal process parameters that maximize reinforcement while minimizing substrate deformation requires an iterative solution model, which has to be representative of the deposition process yet as streamlined as possible to minimize the computational cost. For this purpose, both the coupling of thermal and mechanical simulation is fundamental, as well as building a computationally efficient simulations framework for larger components.

Therefore, like previous literature references [19, 20], the modeling approach adopted aims to maximize the trade-off between accuracy and computational cost by simplifying the deposition simulation. Instead, an analytical deposition model is calibrated using experimental data from single-track depositions. The calibrated model is then used to simulate multi-track deposition to evaluate residual stresses, deformation, and the molten metal dilution into the substrate.

3 Methodology

3.1 DED-LB/P setup and equipment

The DED-LB/P process was performed in a BeAM Magic 800 capable of generating an inert atmosphere in the whole working volume with both O_2 and H_2O content < 100 ppm during the deposition process to avoid reaction of the molten aluminium with oxygen and hydrogen. The system uses an IPG YLS-2000-S2T active fiber laser with 1kW of maximum power and wavelength equal to 1070 nm delivered through a 200 μm fiber and focused in a laser spot of 0.8 mm in diameter. The used feedstock material is AlSi₁₀Mg powder from Eckart TLS GmbH with particle size distribution (PSD) 45 – 105 μm and conveyed to the deposition point with a GTV PF2/2 powder feeder. Argon was used as shielding, forming and carrier gas with fixed flow rates of 3 l/min, 6 l/min, and 3 l/min respectively. The forming gas is used in BeAM's nozzles to shape the powder cone with a longer "depth of field" in its caustic shape.

3.2 Numerical modelling

A numerical model for the simulation of the DED-LB/P process is defined to reproduce the geometrical characteristics of the deposited tracks and to evaluate the mechanical stress and deformations induced in the substrate at the end of the deposition process. The model is implemented using the finite element method software COMSOL Multiphysics®. The simulation domain consists of a specimen in AlSi₁₀Mg, serving as substrate for the deposition. The simulation workflow is divided into two consecutive steps. First, a thermal model is calibrated using experimental deposition results, aiming to build a model that most closely represents the process. Second, the optimized model is used to simulate the deposition of multiple tracks and estimate the resulting substrate deformations via mechanical simulations.

The specimen size for the track fitting process is 75 mm \times 75 mm \times 2 mm. The laser source was modeled as a Gaussian boundary heat source expressed in W/m^2 and multiplied by a constant optical attenuation coefficient β_l to account for the laser shielding due to particle-laser interaction. The variance of the Gaussian distribution R_l was interpreted as proportional to the experimental laser spot radius. The laser moves at constant speed along the y-axis, allowing to use the symmetry plane ZY to reduce the simulation domain and, hence, the computational time and cost. The temperature field was evaluated by solving the heat conduction equation in solids. Particle deposition was modeled to occur within a circular area of radius R_m , co-centered with the laser spot. Non-homogeneous deposition was modeled as a function of the ratio between the distance from the laser position and R_m , adjusted by a constant tuning coefficient β_0 . An optimization solver was used to fit R_l , R_m , β_l and β_0 by minimizing the least squares error between the numerical and experimental shape of the cross sections of one-pass deposited tracks. This approach allows for an accurate assessment of the impact of the deposition on the resulting deformation of the substrate. Further details on the hypothesis and implementation of the thermal model are reported in Supplementary Information.

The model, calibrated on a single-track deposition, was then used to predict the substrate deformation considering multiple passes, following the experimental protocol. The substrate size considered is 150 mm \times 20 mm \times 1.5 mm; in this case, the deposition pattern did not allow the consideration of symmetries to reduce the simulation domain. The mechanical model assumed steady-state conditions,

under the limit of the linear elastic material, treating the sample as free to move and deform, simulating unclamped conditions. The material deformation was attributed exclusively to thermal effects, relating the local strain to the temperature difference between the steady state $T_0 = 25\text{ °C}$ and the stress-free reference temperature T_{eq} . The thermal history of the sample determined its deformation: the deposited material and portion of melted substrate were assumed to have T_{eq} equal to the solidification temperature and to retract during cooling; instead, the remaining substrate material maintained $T_{eq} = T_0$, resulting in substrate bending. Further details on the mechanical model are available in Supplementary Information, as well as the material properties adopted in the simulations.

3.2 Reinforcement structure characterization method

In order to design the reinforcement structures needed on a thin metal sheet, it is necessary to know the mechanical properties and in particular the tensile properties of three subsections: the reinforcement structures manufactured by DED-LB/P, the metal sheet itself, and the section of the metal sheet underneath the applied reinforce, which is subjected to microstructural changes in a region called heat affected zone (HAZ). While the tensile properties of the metal sheet can easily be tested with standardized tensile testing procedures, this is not the case for the reinforcement structures and the HAZ. The microstructure of DED-LB/P material is highly dependent on the geometry, namely the dimension of the part, and it is therefore impossible to manufacture a large volume by DED-LB/P for tensile specimens machining with equal properties to the one of small reinforcement structures consisting of only few layers of material. Therefore, three point bending tests were performed on thin metal sheets with and without reinforcement structures in order to compare the force-strain curve among them and calculate the absorbed energy during the plastic deformation. This results can be later used to design complex reinforcement structures and they could also be compared to simulations to identify the tensile properties of the reinforcement structures considering also the influence of the HAZ.

Three points bending tests were performed in an Instron 100 kN machine with a set deformation speed of 80 mm/s. Rolled AlSi₁Mg plates with dimensions 150 x 20 x 1.5 mm were used as substrate material on top of which AlSi₁₀Mg reinforcement walls were deposited by DED-LB/P with dimensions 110 x 2 x 2.5 mm, centered with respect to the substrate. The material added by DED-LB/P is roughly 16% the mass of the used substrates. A cross section of one of the deposited reinforcement walls is shown in Figure 3b. All tests were performed in as-deposited conditions without heat treatment after the deposition.

To assess the reproducibility of the DED-LB/P process and the quality of the specimens produced, 5 samples of substrates were tested as reference conditions, while 12 samples with reinforcement structures, were tested; 6 of them with the reinforcement on the tensile side of the stresses during deformation and 6 of them with the reinforcement on the compression side. The 3 rollers were manufactured with a diameter of 20 mm and a groove 4 mm deep and 2.5 mm wide to avoid contact with the reinforcement and apply all forces directly onto the substrate. The distance between the two centers of the two rollers on one side was set to 52 mm and the third roller on the opposite side acting in the center.

4 Results

4.1 DED-LB/P parameters development

Influence of process parameters on track's geometry

Process parameters development for slender structures made of AlSi₁₀Mg presents significant challenges in maintaining stable deposition conditions between different layers. Close to the substrate, it is possible to optimize the parameters to deposit tracks with an ideal aspect ratio of track's height over width between 1/3 and 1/4. At higher layers, however, the deposited material is subjected to significantly lower heat dissipation, resulting in longer solidification time of the melt pool and consequently bigger dimension and elongated shape. This longer solidification time, combined with the low surface

tension of molten aluminium, leads to a spread of the melt pool which solidifies in increasingly wider and thinner tracks as well as increasingly deeper dilution in the previously deposited layers. A randomized central composite design (CCD) of experiment with 17 runs including 3 replicates of the center point was performed to investigate the influence of three main process parameters: laser power, deposition speed and powder material feeding rate on the height and width of the tracks, on the melt pool dilution into the substrate, and the presence of pores or defects in the solidified material. All experiments were performed maintaining an inert atmosphere with both O_2 and H_2O values < 100 ppm within the whole working volume of the DED system. In Table 1 the process parameters window used are listed as minimum and maximum values tested during the experimental campaign: axial values of the CCD.

Table 1 Modified parameters window in CCD with minimum and maximum axial values and selected parameters for the reinforcements resulting in aspect ratio 1/3 and no visible material defects

Parameter	Min.	Max.	Selected
Laser power	432 W	768 W	600 W
Speed	830 mm/min	1670 mm/min	1250 mm/min
Powder feeding	1.16 g/min	1.86 g/min	1.5 g/min

Figure 1 From left to right, main effects plots of laser power, speed and powder feeding rate on tracks' height, width and dilution respectively.

Results, summarized in the form of main effect plots shown in Figure 1, pointed out that, within the investigated parameters range, laser power has significant influence (p -value < 0.05) on track's width and material dilution into the substrate, process speed is a significant parameter for track's height and dilution, while the amount of powder feeding only influence significantly the height of the track. All other interactions were proven to be non-significant (p -value > 0.05) with minimal changes of the obtained track geometries with different process parameters values.

Influence of process parameters on material defects

While a clear continuous influence of process parameters on the track's geometry was identified, their influence on the presence of material defects didn't point out any statistically significant factor. Pores bigger than $50 \mu\text{m}$ and lack of fusion defects were, however, only found in tracks printed with laser power of 500 W or lower and in the track with high deposition speed equal to 1670 mm/min, visible in Figure 2b. The selected parameters, shown in Table 1, resulted in a track with only small pores and an aspect ratio very close to 1/3 with height of $245 \mu\text{m}$, width of $779 \mu\text{m}$ and a relatively small dilution into the substrate of $165 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 2 Cross sections of obtained tracks with related parameters of laser power, speed and powder flow: a) excessive track height, b) low track height, c) close to ideal aspect ratio of 1/3

Thin walls made of AlSi10Mg

In DED-LB/P of steels, titanium and nickel based alloys it is usually possible to manufacture thin wall structures by depositing one track on top of each other with uniform width and thickness amongst layers. While depositing AlSi₁₀Mg, on the other hand, the heat accumulation results in longer solidification time of the melt pool and the high liquidity and low surface tension favor the spread of the metal in increasingly wider and thinner layers, making it challenging to control the deposition process. While in the first layer each deposited track has a width of 779 μm and a height of 245 μm, with equal process parameters at higher layers, each deposited track as a width up to 2 mm and a height around 150 μm.

Figure 3 Etched cross sections with visible thinning and widening of the melt pool at higher layers. a) Deposition strategy with two tracks in the first layer, b) depicted deposition strategy for uniform thin wall width

As visible in the etched cross sections of thin wall structures in Figure 3, at higher layers the deposition of additional material causes a significant portion of the previously deposited layers to melt again, leading to a melt pool with a depth up to 0.7 mm. The pressure applied on top of the melt pool by the argon flow coming from the nozzle combined with the longer solidification time lead the melt pool to solidify with a flat top surface, rather than with the characteristic convex shape of DED tracks as in the first few layers. Cross sections also reveal a lateral spray of material from the melt pool, probably also due to the applied pressure from the argon flow, that solidifies along the sides of the thin wall resulting in a wavy lateral surface with visible undercuts.

This change in process characteristics between layers also results in an increase in porosity with higher presence of pores with diameters between 50 and 100 μm. A reduction of energy input, and therefore laser power, at higher layers would seem a logical solution to shorten the solidification time required by the melt pool and avoid the overheating and spreading of the material. Trials proved that a reduction of laser power to 450 W doesn't provide any visible improvement in melt pool dimensional stability, while showing small lack of fusion defects within each track probably due to non-melted powder particles trapped within the melt pool. Further reduction to or below 400 W results in unstable melt pool with varying width along the deposition direction of each track.

4.2 Numerical deposition and thermal deformation

Fitting of model parameters

The first step of the workflow described in Section 3.2 requires the fitting of four model parameters to calibrate the numerical deposition process to the experimental one. The other process parameters, such as laser power and mass flow rate, were chosen to match the "Selected" configuration reported in Table 1. The experimental diameter of the laser spot was considered to be $R_{exp} = 40 \mu\text{m}$, consistent with the methodology described in section 3.1. Therefore, the radius of the Gaussian source and the mass were allowed to vary in the range $0.5 R_{exp} \leq R_l, R_m \leq 2 R_{exp}$. Instead, β_0 and β_l were allowed to vary in the range $[-1 \ 0]$ and $[0 \ 1]$, respectively.

Figure 4 Results of the numerical modeling. a) Comparison between the numerical (red data) and experimental (blue and green data) cross section of the deposited track with the "selected" parameter configuration (see Table 1). b) Shape of the resulting single pass deposited track. c-d) Cross section of the track resulting from a multi-layer deposition, simulated according to the experimental protocol reported in Figure 3. e) Laser penetration inside the substrate, interpreted as the volume of substrate melted by the laser. e) Laser penetration into the substrate, interpreted as the volume of substrate melted by the laser during processing. f-g) Residual von Mises stresses (panel f) and vertical deformation (panel g) after cooling to room temperature.

The results of the model calibration procedure are shown in Figures 4a-b. As it can be observed, the considered experimental profile is slightly asymmetric, probably due to small mismatch in the alignment laser beam-powder nozzle (see also the cross sections reported in Figure 2): therefore, both sides of the track (blue and green data in Figure 4a) were considered in the fitting procedure. The numerical (red data) and experimental cross sections show good agreement; the resulting calibrated model coefficients are listed in Table 2. The calibration was performed considering a single experimental cross section. This step was crucial in order to obtain a coherent and flexible deposition model with reduced computational cost, capable of providing accurate estimates of deposition shape and laser penetration even for more complex and non-straight deposition patterns. Figure 4b shows the simulated deposition track, which appears smooth and regular. In particular, the final part of the deposition recovers the typical inclined plane shape, which in this case exhibits an angle of inclination of about 21°. Note that this was the only type of calibration performed in this study.

Table 2 Parameters of the deposition model calibrated on experimental data.

Parameter	Fitted value
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R_l	0.543 mm
R_m	0.635 mm
β_l	0.528
β_0	-0.223

Fitted model application in multilayer depositions

The calibrated model was then used to simulate multiple depositions. The process pattern considered corresponds to that shown in Figure 3: a first layer of 3 tracks with 0.5 mm spacing on the x-axis and 10 s rest between them; a second layer of 2 tracks with 0.5 mm spacing and shifted by 0.25 on the x-axis with respect to the previous layer; all subsequent layers consist of a single track, all centered in the middle of the substrate. Each track has a length of 110 mm.

The cross section of the deposited material at increasing number of layers, evaluated on a yz-cut plane at the center of the substrate, is shown in Figures 4c-d. The deposition pattern considered causes the tracks in the first layers to partially overlap. Since the model does not account for fluid dynamic effects in the melt pool region, peaks resulting from the summation of two adjacent deposition profiles are formed at the locations of the overlapping depositions (see Figure 4c, blue data). However, these tend to be attenuated by subsequent passes: after the second layer of deposition, the presence of the peaks is negligible (see red data corresponding to the third layer). Furthermore, while the first two layers correctly reproduce the experimental cross sections (compare the lower layers in Figures 3b and Figure 4c), subsequent layers lead to larger discrepancies due to the spreading and thinning of the melt pool as explained in the previous paragraph and due to neglecting the pressure exerted by the shielding gas on the melt pool during solidification. As a result, layers 4-7 steadily increase the thickness of the deposited track, forming a triangular profile instead of stacked sheet-like layers (compare Figure 3a-b and Figure 4d).

Figure 4e also shows the penetration of the laser beam into the substrate, evaluated as the depth at which the substrate melts during the deposition. The first deposited layer reaches a dilution of 0.17 mm, which is similar to the measured value from experimental results of 0.19 mm. Contrary to experimental results, simulation shows a slight increase of dilution while depositing the second and third layer up to a final value of 0.22 mm. This can be explained by the fact that in the experimental campaign the substrate was placed on top of a metallic table, which provides a heat dissipation medium, while the simulation considers only heat dissipation with the surrounding atmosphere, leading to a slightly higher heat accumulation.

Figures 4f-g show the substrate stress and deformation as it was cooled to room temperature. The simulation considered the deposition profile reached after the sixth layer (yellow data in Figure 4d), coherently with the experimental deposition height obtained with the considered process parameters (see Figure 3b). Metal contraction induces significant stresses, with much of the sample exceeding the yield stress (namely, about 230 MPa), especially in the proximity of the deposition track (Figure 4f). Note that the simulation assumes a linear elastic material behavior, so stresses exceeding the yield stress should be interpreted qualitatively. Thermal shrinkage bends the substrate symmetrically by a few millimeters in the yz-plane (Figure 4g). These results suggest that while the deposition process has a minor impact on the specimen, with the laser penetrating and melting approximately 15% of the specimen thickness, subsequent deformation leads to significant material contraction that might be critical to the design of the application considered.

4.3 Simulation-experimental deformation comparison

To further validate the used modelling approach, simulation results of thermal deformation of a thin AlSi₁₂Mg substrate were compared with experimental deformation data obtained by 3D scan of a manufactured sample. The sample geometry consists of a 70 mm long reinforcement structure manufactured with the same strategy depicted in Figure 3b and centered along a 150 x 20 x 1.5 mm substrate. Since the deposition strategy remained unchanged, the fitted coefficients reported in Table 2 were used. During the deposition process, the substrate was clamped for roughly 5 mm along the 20 mm side closer to the start of the deposition, the opposite side, on the other hand, was left unclamped and

free to deform during the deposition process. The results of the comparison in terms of vertical displacement of the substrate are shown in Figure 5. 3D scan results were calculated with a best fit comparison between the measured top surface of the substrate and a CAD of the undeformed substrate.

Remarkably, the experiment and simulation yielded very similar results: the experimental deformation showed a maximum value of +1.5 mm, localized at the extremes of the sample, and a minimum of about -1.4 mm at the center. These results are consistent with the simulation, which reported a maximum vertical deformation of +2.5 mm and a minimum of -1.5 mm, localized at the extremes and the center of the specimen, respectively. The slight overestimation of the deformation is consistent with the geometrical inaccuracies of the deposited material. As visible in Figure 5a, since the substrate was left free to deform on one side while the deposition is ongoing, the DED-LB/P manufactured structure resulted in a height of 2.6 mm on one side and 1.3 mm on the other side as opposed to a planned height of 2.5 mm. The lower addition on material is considered to be the main cause of deviation between the experimental and simulation results. Moreover, a further reason with expected lower impact, is the assumption of a linear elastic material in the simulation, which neglects the energy dissipation due to plastic deformation.

Nevertheless, these results point out a high accuracy of the proposed modelling approach, capable of matching the observed experimental behavior. This was possible despite the used simplifications in the physical model of the deposition process necessary to make the simulation approach applicable to larger parts as well without excessive computational requirements. These model can therefore be used to optimize the printing process of large parts to predict the amount of material that can be added while maintaining the deformations below a predefined limit.

Figure 5 Comparison between experimental (panel a) and numerical (panel b) vertical deformation of a sample following a 70 mm deposition.

4.4 Characterization results of reinforcements

To design reinforcement structures on a thin metal sheet, knowing the tensile properties of three subsections with different microstructures is essential: the reinforcement structures by DED-LB/P, the metal sheet, and the heat affected zone (HAZ). While standardized tensile testing is easy for the metal sheet, it is challenging for the reinforcement structures and HAZ due to the microstructural dependency on geometry in DED-LB/P material. Therefore, three-point bending tests were conducted on thin metal sheets with and without reinforcement to compare force-displacement curves and calculate absorbed energy during plastic deformation using Eq. 1. These results help design complex reinforcement structures and can be compared to simulations to identify tensile properties, considering the HAZ influence.

Three points bending tests were performed with a reinforcement wall on either the tensile or compressive side of the substrate and compare the results to the tests performed on the same substrates without reinforcement. 5 substrates were tested as reference condition while 12 samples with a reinforcement wall were manufactured: 6 to be tested with the reinforcement on the tensile side of the stresses, and 6 with the reinforcement on the compression side.

Reinforcement on tensile side

Results in terms of force-displacement curves for each sample are shown in the graphs in Figure 6. With the reinforcement on the tensile side of the stresses during the 3-point bending test, a stiffening

effect occurs during the first 4 mm of deformation where the forces are visibly higher compared to the substrate alone. Around 4 mm of deformation, however, the more brittle material obtained by DED-LB/P without subsequent heat treatment cracks, leaving the substrate alone to withstand the stresses. Therefore, between 4 and 18 mm of displacement the force-displacement curve of the substrate alone and the substrate with reinforcement on the tensile side are almost identical. On the other hand, after 18 mm of displacement, the stresses are concentrated mainly in the area of the substrate where the reinforcement cracked since it is not subjected to the stiffening effect of the reinforcement anymore. This increased deformation of the material in a specific location, rather than distributed along the sample, leads to a propagation of the crack from the reinforcement wall into the substrate, causing high variability in the results for this point on, with two samples fracturing completely before the maximum deformation of 30 mm and an average force-displacement curve lower than the one of the substrate alone.

Reinforcement on compression side

When the reinforcement material is placed on the compression side of the stresses during the 3 point bending test, results show a significant improvement of the performances along the entire force-displacement curve, with forces reaching values up to 90% higher than the condition with the substrate alone. Apart from the possible differences in tensile and compression material properties of the DED-LB/P reinforcement, a hypothesis to explain the large improvement in these results is that even in the case of cracking of the brittle reinforcement, the compressive stresses act to close the crack creating friction between the sides of the crack which keeps providing a stiffening effect to the substrate.

Figure 6 Results of 3 points bending tests on a) substrates only b) substrate with reinforcement by DED-LB/P on the tensile side, c) substrate with reinforcement by DED-LB/P on the compression side. In Figure 6b the three identified subsections with different behavior of the material are highlighted.

Energy absorption

To compare the results amongst them and quantify the performance improvement between the tested conditions, it was decided to calculate the energy absorption of each tested sample from the discretized data of force and displacement with the equation:

$$E [J] = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (D_{i+1} - D_i) \left(\frac{F_{i+1} + F_i}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where D_i represent the displacement values in mm and F_i the measured forces in kN. The energy absorbed from each sample up to a maximum deformation of 30 mm is calculated and averaged, as shown in Table 3. Moreover, energy absorption was also calculated up to a deformation value of 20 mm to compare the reinforcement capabilities before the propagation of the cracks and the high variability in results with reinforcement on the tensile side takes place.

As seen from the force-displacement graphs, energy absorption values point out a marginal increase in energy absorbed with the addition of a reinforcement wall on the tensile side of the stresses with an increase of only 2.4% considering that the mass increase of the samples is about 16%. Also, from the analysis of the first 20 mm of deformation alone, the increase in energy absorption given by the

DED-LB/P material is 5.1%. On the other hand, the energy absorption provided by the reinforcement on the compression side of the stresses resulted in an average increase of 75.8%.

Table 3 Calculated average energy absorption and standard deviation of results for deformations up to 30 and 20 mm during 3-point bending test.

	Substrate only	Reinf. tensile	Reinf. compression
Average energy 30 mm	9.79 J	10.02 J (+2.4%)	17.21 J (+75.8%)
St. dev. energy 30 mm	0.07 J	0.77 J	0.82 J
Average energy 20 mm	6.92 J	7.27 J (+5.1%)	12.10 J (+74.8%)
St. dev. energy 20 mm	0.04 J	0.21 J	0.54 J

This difference in performance of the reinforcement structure acting on the compression or tensile side of the stresses can be attributed to the fact that the DED-LB/P without heat treatment is known to be more brittle than the rolled substrates. As soon as the material cracks on the tensile side, it stops providing any sort of reinforcement and all the stresses act on the substrate alone. Moreover the initiated crack in the reinforcement can further develop into the substrate leading to even lower performance at high deformation values compared to the substrate alone. On the other hand, with the DED-LB/P material on the compressive side, even in case of crack initiation the material would keep providing a reinforcement since the stresses tend to close the crack.

While these results pointed out the capability of reinforcement structures by DED-LB/P to stiffen thin metal sheets for small deformations, they also pointed out that, in case of large plastic deformations, to significantly increase the toughness (e.g. energy absorption during deformation), a heat treatment is necessary to increase the ductility of the applied reinforcements. The performed characterization by three point bending test of the reinforcement provided by a single straight wall applied by DED-LB/P, allows to get the needed data and material properties to design reinforcements with complex and integrate geometries, such as triangular or honeycomb structures. The design of more complex reinforcement geometries, enabled by the design freedom of DED technologies, allows to tailor the final properties of the reinforced metal sheet to the application requirements, adding significant value to a simple substrate material. Moreover, these results also showed that during the design of the reinforcements, it is crucial to consider the way the part is going to deform under the expected stresses to take into account the different properties of the reinforcements when subjected to either tensile or compressive stresses.

5 Conclusions

Results of this work pointed out that:

1. AlSi₁₀Mg reinforcement structures can be manufactured by DED-LB/P onto 1.5 mm thick aluminium substrates. By optimizing both process parameters and deposition strategy, it is possible to minimize the HAZ and keep the thermal deformations relatively low.
2. The proposed simplified modelling approach allows for easy calibration and accurate simulation of the deposition, resulting in a good comparability with the experimental deposition. In addition, simulation of substrate residual stresses and deformations show significant material contraction after deposition, consistent with experimental results, which may have major implications in geometrical accuracy for large parts. This methodology could be leveraged to reduce the need for extensive characterization campaigns, including also non-straight deposition patterns, while maintaining experimental representativeness and a low computational cost.
3. Synergistic interaction between experiments and the model can be used in future studies to design optimized reinforcements on complex subcomponents, e.g. reticular patterns, allowing to tailor the mechanical behavior of the whole part with minimal addition of extra material.
4. When DED-LB/P reinforcement structures made of AlSi₁₀Mg are subjected to tensile stresses, the brittle material of the reinforcement tends to crack soon. This leads to three visible sections along the force-displacement curves: a stiffening effect with higher force until cracking,

the substrate withstanding alone to the deformations and a detrimental effect due to the concentration of the deformation in a single point of the substrate. This results to an average energy absorption improvement of only 2.4% during 3 points bending tests. Heat treatment should be considered in this case to improve the ductility of the deposited material.

5. When DED-LB/P reinforcement structures made of AlSi₁₀Mg are subjected to compressive stresses, the specimens withstand the imposed deformation with force up to 90% higher than the substrate along and average energy absorption increase by 75.8% with a related mass increase of the specimen of 16%. These results point out the importance of the prediction of the deformation direction while designing the reinforcement structure to act mainly on the compression side of the stresses in the final component.

6 Supplementary material

Supplementary information includes descriptions of the thermal and mechanical models used to simulate the deposition process and virtually characterize the substrates. Additionally, the thermal and mechanical properties of AlSi10Mg adopted in the simulations are also included.

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